

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES THROUGH MODERN METHODS

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ABSTRACT

This article is intended to give basic information on the innovative and useful methods used in teaching foreign language to students and provides important information on developing students' interest in language learning with the help of different methods. Compared with traditional education teaching methods, the advantages of the modern educational technology, teaching is obvious, but still can not ignore the dominant position of teachers in the teaching process. In the actual teaching process, the outstanding teachers' vivid explanation, concise writing on the blackboard and the timely exchange of feedback between teachers and students are very necessary. The key to teaching is that teachers should be based on the previous teaching work to carefully prepare lessons, make system design and correct use modern educational technology and innovative methods as well.

The concepts of "method", "methodology" and "technology" are widely used in pedagogical activity. However, it is possible to form a clear definition of concepts through the analysis of the literature, the generalization of information. creates a unique teaching method that serves to achieve. The resolution of the Government "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" laid the foundation for the popularization of English among the population of Uzbekistan. This decision envisages a radical reform of the system of teaching foreign languages, its organization at the level of modern requirements. Given that there are so many suggestions for teaching English, "Which method do you teach?" In

our turbulent times, when the education market offers all kinds of courses in language teaching, time is of the essence and gold is a business. Those who want to study and develop their business often choose short courses such as "Learn English in Two Weeks", "Effective Express Method", "Analytical English" and others, how effective are these teaching methods? Do they give the expected result?

In the recent past, the teaching of English has focused on grammar. Today, the main supply in the language market is formed according to consumer demand. But modern language learners are not interested in the history of the language or its theory. English has become necessary for them to meet their vital needs. Several

methods are currently offered to students studying English. One of them is the fundamental method. It requires at least 2-3 years of study, in-depth study of grammar. This method is mainly used in the training of professional translators. Based on it, language is studied as a real and complete means of communication. At present, the fundamental method has not changed its purpose, but many other methods have entered the field of competition with the fundamental method. The most important thing in the learning process is how accurate the content of the transmitted information is. A university student should not only excel in reading, writing and translating in English, but should also be able to see English in the context of a different folk culture.

This is exactly what an English teacher should pay attention to in the language teaching process. In addition to the textbook, Headway Pronunciation is included to improve pronunciation. In today's fast-paced world, another popular method of teaching English is the "intensive method." It is not possible to learn English in 2 weeks using the intensive method, but hard-working, self-working students can easily learn the language in 3 months. They can be a stimulus for the student to learn the language faster. In conclusion, it is known that there are a variety of educational institutions in the country, so for the purpose of teaching in these educational institutions. It is advisable to have a separate foreign language teaching methodology.

Natural and social phenomena develop in an interconnected and continuous relationship. None of this is because the sciences are the reflection of

objective reality does not exist in isolation from others. An event and a subject can be a source of research for many disciplines at the same time, for example, the study of the social phenomenon of "language" from its point of view linguistics (psychology), psychology (psychology), pedagogy (didactics). The term "foreign language methodology" evokes in the human mind the association of "connection": first, a set of methods and methodological approaches to language teaching, or scientific knowledge of teaching methods, and finally, independent pedagogical science comes to mind. The methodology of teaching a foreign language has developed in accordance with didactics, in an interconnected way. It is well known that the teaching theories of all disciplines are based on the science of didactics, from which they receive scientific nourishment. Foreign language teaching is also based on didactics. General theory of didactic education, methodology is considered as a science of teaching a certain subject, lingvodidactics is considered as a general theory of teaching languages, linguomethodology is considered as a science of teaching a specific language. The term "method" means the method of work of the teacher-teacher and the student in the acquisition of knowledge, skills, abilities, the formation of worldviews in students and the creation of opportunities for learning. This concept has countless definitions. The application of methods in foreign language teaching dates back a long time, and principles are relatively new methodological terms. Historically, the methods have been grouped into four groups, and their names have been adopted as "translation," "correct," "comparative," and "mixed."

History of methods. The famous Methodist prof. In-depth study by I.V Rakhmanov. The method of translation is mainly in two forms and is called grammar-translation and text-translation methods. From the point of view of grammar-translation method, a foreign language is studied for general educational purposes. Grammar exercises are designed to develop the learner's logical thinking. Explaining grammatical knowledge is considered to be the main goal of teaching. The main principles of this method are:

1. Language learning is based on written speech.
2. Grammar was taken as the subject of study, and the vocabulary was chosen accordingly. Doing grammar exercises was the main way to work.
3. First, the grammatical rule is memorized, and then it is recommended to make sentences based on the rules.
4. The grammatical form and meaning of the words are revealed through literal translation.
5. Language material is mastered through literal translation and dry memorization.
6. Limited to individual memorization of words, out of context.

The term intercultural communication is now widely used in foreign language teaching methods. It is this concept that we can apply in a variety of contexts. In fact: Intercultural dialogue is the dialogue of different cultures about their social origin, mentality, national character, lifestyle, customs, value system, etc. In this process, it is necessary to educate and develop students in the spirit of respect, patience and understanding of the culture of another country. Every foreign language lesson is a crossroads of

cultures, a practice of intercultural communication. Because every word in a foreign language in this process reflects a foreign life and culture. The task of teachers is to develop the communicative ability of pupils and students. To do this, it is necessary to master textbooks that teach people to communicate effectively and new teaching methods aimed at developing four speech activities in a foreign language.

Basically, in teaching foreign languages, modern education technology has also a great importance because, they can be very beneficial to improve all skills of languages. Modern education technology is a new branch of education, based on modern teaching theory as a guide and science and technology as a means, scientifically integrating teaching process and learning resources, the theory and practice of achieving the purpose of teaching optimization. Modern education technology emphasizes the improvement of traditional teaching methods and teaching skills, pay attention to the rational use of teaching media in the teaching process, optimize the teaching process, and thus improve the quality of education and teaching. The scientific application of modern educational technology in practical teaching has made great changes in teaching communication methods, teaching content presentation methods, teaching methods and teaching organization forms, and has led to fundamental changes in the related educational concepts, educational system and so on, breaking the traditional education model, pooling a new era of breath into the entire education and teaching process.

The Influence of Modern Educational Technology on Education.

1) The high efficiency and high quality of modern educational technology in information storage, transmission and presentation can make the learners in different places communicate with teachers through the Internet and through satellite transmission and interactive TV. The traditional class teaching system model, teaching activities and teaching organization produce a fundamental change.

2) Modern educational technology can take scattered teaching content and teaching examples together and form a system to optimize the teaching content and teaching process, and then improve teaching efficiency and teaching quality.

3) Modern educational technology using media tools to simulate the reality, to solve abstract teaching content in the traditional teaching process, making the whole learner in learning process has a strong intuitive and self-operation, conducive to learners to carry out image understanding analysis, so that learners in their learning process tends to take the initiative, in a dominant position.

4) Modern educational technology can realize the two-way interaction between teachers and learners in the process of teaching and learning. Learners use their computers to develop their own learning methods according to their own learning habits. Teachers use the specific teaching software to evaluate learners' learning results. It fundamentally realized the differentiation of learners' learning, and embodied the teaching principles of "teaching students in accordance with their aptitude".

5) Modern educational technology using a variety of modern communication technology for information exchange and transmission, so that modern distance learning become possible. Not limited to time and space, learners can through the network to learn effectively, significantly reducing learning costs.

In conclusion, learning a foreign language is a multifaceted doctrine, in the process of which a person experiences complex psychological changes. In particular, there is a process of comparing a native language with a foreign language. Different teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. Using modern pedagogical technologies, comparative teaching of a foreign language with the native language gives effective results. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. Methodology and technology play an important role in the process of learning a foreign language. There are different methods of methodical science in the organization of the lesson. The most widely used methods of teaching a foreign language are: the method of communicative didactics, the method of organizing intercultural communication and the method of organizing exercises. The three methods are closely related to each other and complement each other. Because the science of methodology is related to the science of didactics, it is based on communicativeness during the study of a foreign language, and the method of communicative didactics emerges.

So, modern, intensive methods have contributed considerable energy to the method of teaching foreign languages in

general. Achievements of intensive methods in the field of activating the processes of perception and assimilation of the material basis of communication, in opening up its reserves of motivation and

in developing adequate forms of collective interaction should as soon as possible become the property of teaching methods at the university, to develop its effectiveness and efficiency.

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